

Changes in longevity, parasitization rate and development time of the whitefly parasitoid *Encarsia formosa* under future climate conditions

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Fitness parameters of *Encarsia formosa* were assessed in two climate conditions.
- Future climate of Central Europe (FCCE) will accelerate *E. formosa* development.
- FCCE will increase *E. formosa* parasitization rate on whiteflies.
- FCCE will reduce *E. formosa* adult longevity.

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ABSTRACT

Biological control by augmentative release of parasitoids is an established practice for controlling an economically very important insect pest group, whiteflies (Aleyrodidae), in protected cropping systems worldwide. One of the two most used parasitoids is *Encarsia formosa*. Anthropogenic climate change will modify multitrophic interactions between organisms, and sensitive biocontrol systems are not an exception. At the same time, there is a knowledge gap in our understanding of the performance of *E. formosa* as a biocontrol agent in mid-future climate. In the present study, we evaluate the parasitization rate, development time, and longevity of this important biocontrol agent by performing climatic chamber simulation driven by physically consistent, regionally downscaled, numerical future climate projections. The parasitoid shows 8.6 days accelerated development, 15-fold higher parasitization rate, and 38% shorter longevity under the tested future climate conditions. Challenges in conclusively assessing life parameters of this parasitoid, and the implications on whitefly biocontrol in the future are discussed.

1. Introduction

Whiteflies (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) are an insect pest group responsible for high losses in global agriculture (Byrne and Bellows Jr 1991, Li et al. 2021, Stansly and Naranjo 2010). They feed on the phloem of hundreds of plant species which leads to stunted growth, chlorosis, and wilting. During probing and feeding, whiteflies also transmit several important viruses which often cause even more substantial secondary damage to their hosts (Fiallo-Olivé et al. 2020), and excrete honeydew on which the sooty mold develops. The most damaging whiteflies species for horticultural crops are *Trialeurodes*

vaporarium (Westwood) and *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius) species complex (Boykin 2014, Liu, Colvin and De Barro 2012, Milenovic et al. 2019, Nasruddin and Mound 2016, Wintermantel 2004). Whiteflies have a global distribution, although most species are found in the tropical regions. In Europe, whiteflies have a distribution limitation based on the temperatures of the winter season (Gilioli et al., 2014). In Central Europe, *T. vaporarium* and *B. tabaci* are present year-round in protected cropping systems, while *T. vaporarium* is also present in the open field during the summer cropping season (Cuthbertson et al. 2011). Both species are not capable to overwinter in the open field in Central Europe. Luxembourg, which is located at the latitudinal midpoint of

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Central Europe, is often referred as a “test bed” and a good representative of the climate of the region.

Control of whiteflies is challenging, and with the push towards reduced use of pesticides and insecticide resistance development, global control methods rely increasingly on established and widely used biocontrol strategy (Horowitz et al. 2020, Rodríguez, Téllez and Janssen 2019). This means conservation of natural enemies in the open field by optimized insecticide use (Naranjo 2001, Rapisarda et al., 2018), and augmentative release of natural enemies in protected cropping systems. Most commonly used biocontrol agents in protected systems are parasitoid wasps of the genera *Encarsia* (Foerster) and *Eretmocerus* (Halderman) (Hymenoptera: Aphelinidae) (Gerling, Alomar and Arnó 2001), and generalist predators such as ladybugs (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae), mirid bugs (Hemiptera: Miridae), lacewings larvae (Neuroptera: Chrysopidae) and other species (Gerling, Alomar and Arnó 2001, Li et al. 2011). *Encarsia formosa* (Gahan) and *Eretmocerus eremicus* (Rose and Zolnerowich) are currently the most widely available and used parasitoids.

One of the challenges of effective and consistent biocontrol is the dependence of this multitrophic system on the optimal climatic conditions. Today, the climate, defined in a narrow sense as the “average weather” (IPCC, 2012), is changing at the global scale, and these changes are very likely the biggest challenge for the humanity on the 21st century, especially for agriculture (Arias et al. 2021). Insect pests, including whiteflies, might cause greater damage in the future climate, and more research is needed to understand this potential future threat (Gilioli et al. 2014).

The constant rise in CO₂ concentration since the dawn of the industrial age in the late 18th century, set to exceed 1000 ppm by 2100, is driving a global temperature increase. This means mean global temperature increase of anywhere from 1.5 °C to 4 °C depending on the mitigation measures implemented (Arias et al. 2021). Advances in numerical climate modelling have enabled detailed projections even at a scale fine enough to support climate change adaptation strategies in agriculture (Allan et al. 2021). The use of a multi-model ensemble approach by combining results of several regional climate models into one projection outperforms the individual member model results (Semenov and Stratonovitch 2010, Tebaldi and Knutti 2007). The projected climate change leads to a cascade of effects across the ecosystems which are more difficult to predict than the climate itself. The difficulty largely comes from the lack of knowledge about how organisms and multi-organism interactions respond to the changes in their environment (Tylianakis et al. 2008).

If no action is taken to better understand and reduce the action of climate change on insects, there will be a reduction in our ability to build a sustainable future based on healthy, functional ecosystems (Harvey et al., 2023).

Temperature fluctuations can follow predictable or unpredictable patterns (Costaz et al., 2023). Small ectotherm insects like parasitoids and their hosts are expected to react with phenotypic plasticity in case of the former or bet-hedging in case of the latter (Le Lann, van Baaren and Visser, 2021; Costaz et al., 2023). Higher temperatures can exacerbate a reduction in the success rate of parasitoid biocontrol. For example, differences in Thermal Performance Curves between the parasitoid and its host, resulting in a thermal mismatch in part of the temperature range, are expected under future climate (Costaz et al., 2023; Furlong and Zalucki, 2017).

Currently, most models of how organisms, especially insect pest, respond to climate change are based on life tables, which describe organism's performance at discrete levels of individual environmental parameters (usually air temperature, sometimes including relative humidity, and rarely other parameters). The life tables are experimentally determined by measuring developmental parameters while individually varying environmental variables. This approach simplify the environmental factors that delineate a complex real world climate scenario, considering the effects of a single factor (i.e. temperature) singularly. In

order to assess how future climate could impact on these biosystems, an approach using climate projection depicting future climate scenarios could be adopted. Recently, such simulation was performed in a climatic chamber and evaluated the climate change effect on the whitefly *B. tabaci* MED (Milenovic et al. 2023a). The simulation showed nearly 50% reduction of *B. tabaci* development time in the next 50 years in Central European environment, and a deviation from the expected prediction based solely on the life tables. The actual changes in the damages caused by whiteflies in the future will depend on many interacting factors, including the performance (development time, survival, parasitization rate, etc.) of parasitoids which are also heavily influenced by the environmental factors (Asplen, Hardin and Byrne 2009, McCutcheon and Simmons 2001, Qiu et al. 2006, Zandi-Sohani and Shishehbor 2011). Increase in air temperature (up to a point) means shorter development time but also shorter longevity for parasitoid of the genus *Encarsia* (Qiu et al. 2006, Zandi-Sohani and Shishehbor 2011). Short-term extremes temperatures, likely to become more common under future climate scenario, showed to have a detrimental effect on *E. formosa* growth and reproduction (Li et al., 2023). The effect of increased CO₂ concentration on its own seems to have mostly neutral effect on both whiteflies and their parasitoids (Wang et al. 2014, Zandi-Sohani and Shishehbor 2011). Higher relative humidity generally favors parasitoids, although not many studies focused on impact of relative humidity on whitefly parasitoid fitness (Lacey et al. 1999, Sengonca and Liu 1998).

Considering the number of pest species with high risk of poleward expansion and their unique biocontrol strategy, more data on the species performance under future climate is highly needed. The present study sets the hypothesis that physically consistent simulations of the mid-term future Central European climate would cascade in direct effect on the parasitoid fitness. Under future climate whiteflies are expected to overwinter further north than the actual distribution (Gilioli et al., 2014; Milenovic et al. 2023a). Considering that *E. formosa* can be found established as local populations in southern Europe (Drobnjaković et al., 2016), assessing how future climate will impact on the fitness of the parasitoid is a critical question to predict its success in biocontrol. In the present work, we assess the development, parasitization rate, and longevity of a whitefly parasitoid, *E. formosa*, in the present and projected future climate of Luxembourg using physical climatic chamber simulation.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Observational data and climate projections

Present (long-term average) and the projected mid-term future (2061–2070) climate of Luxembourg was simulated in two climatic chambers (Bronson Climate BV, The Netherlands). Diurnal courses of temperature and relative humidity were obtained from an automatic weather station located in Obercorn, Luxembourg (49° 51' N, 5° 90' E, 378 m above mean sea level), which is since 2006 part of the official agrometeorological network of Luxembourg. Long-term hourly values (2006–2015) were obtained from the data archive operated by the “Administration des services techniques de l'agriculture” (ASTA). Based on the data, a long-term hourly diurnal course of mean July air temperatures was calculated for the entire period. Based on the daily mean air temperature and the daily variation, a representative day was determined to be 19.07.2007.

Previously published regional climate projections for Luxembourg were used for the climate change impact assessments (Goergen et al. 2013, Junk, Goergen and Krein 2019). The climate time series to drive the climatic chamber simulations were derived from regional climate projections taken from the Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment project (CORDEX, <https://www.cordex.org>). A multi-model ensemble, with eight ensemble members, of regional climate models for the RCP8.5 emission scenarios (Representative Concentration Pathway)

was used to simulate physically consistent future air temperature, relative humidity, and CO₂ levels for the timespan 2061–2070. A multi-model mean of the daily long-term July air temperatures and humidity projections were calculated and the differences added to the original time series taken from the ASTA station.

The final hourly time series used as the “present” and “future” programs for the climate chambers are available in the [supplementary material \(Table S1\)](#). In summary, present climate program had a mean temperature of 19.8 °C, relative humidity (RH) of 69.2% and 410 ppm of CO₂, while “future” program had a mean temperature of 23.4 °C, 67.5% RH, and 700 ppm of CO₂. Light was provided by the integrated Valoya NS12 (Valoya, Helsinki, Finland) luminaries, set to 480 μmol/m² s PPFD at 20 cm distance in both climatic chambers.

2.2. Insect material

E. formosa parasitized *T. vaporariorum* nymphs were purchased (“En-Strip” strips, Koppert, Belgium), unpacked immediately after delivery, and kept in closed glass petri dishes at room temperature (22 ± 1 °C) to allow the adult emergence. Newly emerged adults were captured using glass capillary tube aspirator and kept for at least two and no more than 24 h at room temperature before being used for experiments.

2.3. *Encarsia formosa* longevity under climate change conditions

About 450 adults per climate condition were used for the no-host longevity experiment. Petri dish containing hatched *E. formosa* adults was carefully opened under a magnifying lens and adults were aspirated using a mouth aspirator. They were separated in equal groups between the climates in different glass vials (8 × 3 Ø cm) per climate, with a fine mesh cap to allow air exchange. Immediately after transferring the parasitoid adults, one 8 ± 3 mm cotton ball soaked in 300 μl diluted honey (50% *Robinia pseudoacacia* L. honey, 50% tap water) was added and left on the same position in the vial throughout the whole experiment. An additional no-diet control vial was included in both climate experiments, containing non-soaked pressed cotton ball. A total of 11 vials with honey and two no-diet control vials were prepared per climate. The vials were uniquely labeled and placed in the two separate climatic chambers set to two different climatic conditions. Dead individuals in each vial were counted daily (excluding weekends) until no living individuals remained. Insects dead during the weekend were counted on the following working day.

2.4. *Encarsia formosa* parasitization rate and developmental time

Before the purchase of *E. formosa* parasitoids, approximately 150 unsexed whitefly adults were confined to a single fully developed tomato leaflet by means of a clip cage (4 × 4 Ø cm) and removed after 48 h oviposition. A total of 26 clip cages were used, 13 in each climate, with 1–2 cages per plant. This method ensured an oversupply of host nymphs (i.e. a higher number of host available than the expected parasitization for the given time). When the whiteflies reached 2nd–3rd nymphal stage, clip cages were introduced again, and three parthenogenic *E. formosa* females were introduced to each cage for a 72-hour oviposition, then their status was recorded as alive or dead (including missing) and they were removed from the clip cages. *B. tabaci* nymphs, either parasitized or healthy, were left developing undisturbed. All the cages were checked daily for the presence of newly emerged parasitoids; when present, they were counted and isolated. Part of them were re-directed to the longevity test, and their survival was assessed over time in the same conditions mentioned in the paragraph above. In this way the F1 generations were reared for their life in one of the two climates, enabling an overall assessment of their lifetime fitness in the two different climatic conditions. After parasitoid emergence, the total number of parasitized and non-parasitized whitefly exuviae was counted for each leaf.

2.5. Statistical analysis

All statistical analyses were conducted using R software v 4.1.2 employing a similar methodology to [Ripamonti et al. \(2022\)](#) and [Milenovic et al. \(2023b\)](#). Raw data were cleaned using packages `dplyr`, `tidyr`, `stringr` ([Wickham 2019](#), [Wickham 2020](#), [Wickham et al. 2020](#)).

Encarsia formosa developmental time (from egg laid on a parasitized *B. tabaci* nymph to adult emergence) and longevity (time from adult emergence to death) were estimated through Kaplan-Meier estimates ([Kaplan and Meier 1958](#)) as implemented in the R package ‘`survival`’, measuring the probability of survival from the beginning of the experiment to the event of interest (emergence or death; [Figs. 1 and 2](#), respectively). Log-Rank test (=Mantel-Haenszel test) was implemented on the developmental time data, by means of the ‘`survdiff`’ function of the ‘`survival`’ package ([Therneau 2021](#)). Generalized Additive Cox Model ([Hastie and Tibshirani 2017](#), [Wood 2011](#)) was applied to the longevity dataset, with Peto’s correction for ties as implemented in the package ‘`mgcv`’. GAM model was chosen due to non-proportional hazards of the Cox Hazard Ratio Model. Covariate (climate and diet) effects were graphically represented by Aalen’s Additive Regression Model (package ‘`survival`’, function ‘`aareg`’, [Supplementary Material S2](#)) ([Therneau 2021](#)). Vial identity was added to the model as a random effect. GAM results were subjected to EMMs comparisons ([Lenth 2022](#)), with Tukey’s p-value adjustment and all-pairwise comparisons ([Hot-horn, Bretz and Westfall 2008](#)). Summary statistics tables were produced ([Tables 1, 2, and 3](#)) and paired with the results from all pairwise comparisons for [Table 2](#).

The development curves were joined with the survival (longevity) curves of the same F1 individuals. The area under joint development-survival curves were calculated using trapezoidal integration as implemented in the ‘`trapz`’ function of the R package ‘`pracma`’ ([Borchers 2016](#)).

Parasitization rate was assessed through a Generalized Linear Mixed Model with Negative Binomial distribution (‘`glmm.nb`’ function, ‘`lme4`’ package; [Bates et al., 2015](#)), with climate, number of available *B. tabaci* nymphs, and residual alive adults after 72 h oviposition as fixed effects, and single clip-cage as random effect. Model performances were analyzed with the ‘`performance`’ ([Lüdecke et al. 2021](#)) and ‘`DHARMA`’ ([Hartig and Hartig 2017](#)) packages.

R packages used for analyses and production of figures were ‘`survival`’ ([Therneau 2021](#)), ‘`survminer`’ ([Kassambara et al., 2020](#)), ‘`ggplot2`’ ([Wickham 2016](#)).

The raw datasets are available at [OSF.io \(https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/ZA6VK\)](https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/ZA6VK), while the complete R code for data analysis is publicly available on GitHub (<https://github.com/matteo-rpm/papers>).

3. Results

The parasitoid showed mean development time of 26.6 (interquartile range (IQR) = 4) days in the present and 18.0 (IQR = 2) days in the future climate, which is about 70% of the present development time ([Table 1](#)). The overall difference in development was found as statistically significant (Log-Rank test: $\chi^2 = 57.9$, $df = 1$, $p = 3e-14$). Development curves (Kaplan-Meier estimates) are presented in [Fig. 1](#).

The longevity of original Koppert En-Strip adults (F0), captured second generation adults (F1), as well as no-diet controls is presented in [Fig. 2](#). F0 adults had mean longevity of 36.2 (IQR = 13) and 22.4 (IQR = 12) days in present and future climate respectively, which meant 38% shorter longevity under future climate ([Table 2](#)). In case of the F1 adults, the longevity was 42% shorter in the future climate, and took 26.1 (IQR = 10.5) and 15.2 (IQR = 8) days on average under the present and future conditions, respectively ([Table 2](#)). Although future climatic conditions resulted in similar shortening of the adult longevity of about 40%, the F1 adults in both climates had shorter lifespan (by about 10 days) than those of F0 ([Table 2](#) and [Fig. 2](#)). Adults in no-diet controls lived only four

Fig. 1. Development curves (Kaplan-Meier estimates) of F1 adult *Encarsia formosa* compared under two different climate conditions: present climate (2006–2015, green line) and future climate (2061–2070, red line). The x-axis represents the emergence day, measured in days after the oviposition, while the y-axis represents the emergence rate from 0 (0%) to 1 (100%). The horizontal dashed line represents 50% of emergence. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 2. Survival curves (Kaplan-Meier estimates) of F0 (solid lines) and F1 (dashed lines) adult *Encarsia formosa* under no-diet control treatment (grey lines), and present (2006–2015, green lines) and future (2061–2070, red lines) climate conditions. The x-axis represents the death day, measured in days after the emergence, while the y-axis represents the survival rate from 0 (0%) to 1 (100%). The horizontal dashed line represents 50% of mortality. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Table 1
Summary statistics for *Encarsia formosa* nymphal development under present (2006–2015) and future climate conditions (2061–2070). n: total number of individuals; IQR: inter-quartile range; Q1: first quartile (25th percentile); Q3: third quartile (75th percentile).

Climate	n	Mean	Median	IQR	Q1	Q3
present	12	26.6	26	4	24	28
future	164	18.0	18	2	17	19

and three days in the present and future climate respectively (Table 2). The difference between all groups was statistically significant as presented in Table 2.

Combining the development and the survival of F1 individuals, as presented in Fig. 3, the area under the curve was calculated to be 28.6, and 27.3 for the present and future curve, respectively.

Mean parasitization of Koppert En-Strip *E. formosa* individuals was 1.2 (IQR = 1.8) parasitized nymphs per clip cage in the present climate, and 18.2 (IQR = 14) in the future climate, according to the number of emerged second generation adults (Table 3). This counting method was more accurate compared to the count of whitefly exuviae containing a characteristic round exit hole, and dark color at the end of the experiment which resulted in lower counts in both climates (Table 3). The difference between two climates was statistically significant despite the relatively low number of parasitized nymphs in the present climate (Table 4). As expected, the number of whitefly nymphs available for parasitization differed between two climates and was 73 (IQR = 34.5) and 168 (IQR = 76) on average per clip cage in the present and future climate, respectively (Table 3). In each cage, the number of available host nymphs was several times higher than highest seen parasitization count in any of the cages across the treatments, thus representing a non-limiting factor for parasitization.

4. Discussion

To our knowledge, this is the first work assessing the impact of projected future climate on the whitefly parasitoid *Encarsia formosa* (Gahan). Performing a physical simulation driven by the output of numerical climate projections, we tested *E. formosa* longevity in generations F0 (commercially available population) and F1 (subjected to climate simulations from egg to death), F1 developmental time, and F0 parasitization rate in present and projected future climate conditions. Besides focusing on singular environmental factors when constructing life tables, our approach of simulating a complex climate scenario with daily diurnal cycles in temperatures and humidity with different CO₂ concentration could be more descriptive of the climate in which these insects will develop in the future.

Evaluating the potential impact of future climate on *E. formosa* fitness is critical for predicting its effectiveness in whiteflies biocontrol. Previous results showed a similar impact of future climate on the longevity of another whitefly Aphelinidae parasitoid, *Eretmocerus eremicus* (Milenovic et al., 2023b). The effects of these abiotic conditions

Table 2
Summary statistics for *Encarsia formosa* adult longevity under present (2006–2015) and future climate conditions (2061–2070). n: total number of individuals; IQR: inter-quartile range; Q1: first quartile (25th percentile); Q3: third quartile (75th percentile). Comparisons between rows were conducted after a General Additive Model (GAM) with Cox proportional hazard family. Post hoc pairwise comparisons were conducted with least-square means method and Tukey method for p-value adjustment, at significance level as 0.05 and 95% confidence intervals, and represented by letters for every specific group. Specifics in Supplementary Material S2.

Climate	Diet	Generation	n	Mean	Median	IQR	Q1	Q3	Pairwise comparisons
present	honey	F0	303	36.2	39	13	33	46	a
present	honey	F1	7	26.1	27	10.5	21	31.5	
future	honey	F0	329	22.4	25	12	18	30	b
future	honey	F1	40	15.2	16	8	13	21	
present	no-diet	F0	123	4.0	4	1	3	4	c
future	no-diet	F0	140	3.0	3	0	3	3	d

seem similar among the two parasitoid species. Moreover, as already mentioned, whiteflies will also be affected by future climate (Milenovic et al. 2023a). Our results show substantially increased parasitization rate under the future climate, together with reduced development time and reduced adult longevity. Considering the life parameters in the future conditions compared to present, the development will be shortened by 8.6 days, the parasitization rate will increase 15-fold, and shortening of adult longevity by 13.8 days. The overall pattern is consistent with temperature-dependent development observed in insects. This means that as whitefly development gets shorter in the future (Milenovic et al. 2023a), and spring population build-up becomes faster, the parasitoid development is likely to follow accordingly. Moreover, it is important to notice that Aphelinidae parasitization ability reach its maximum within the first days after adult emergence (Qiu et al., 2004). Considering this, and the fact that under protected cropping systems the release of these parasitoid is usually happening at least once per week (Tello et al., 2007), the expected reduction in longevity seems less trivial in the context of biocontrol.

However, fitness parameters of *E. formosa* show considerable variability between populations. Drobnjaković et al. (2016) compared female longevity in seven populations collected in Serbia and showed how the population with highest no-host longevity lived for 21 days compared to only 10 days in the population with shortest longevity, despite identical methodology. Similarly, Qiu et al. (2004) compared populations from Koppert facility in Netherlands to a field collected population from Maryland, USA, and showed that Koppert population had shorter longevity, faster development at higher temperatures, but similar parasitization rates. The host plant can also significantly affect the development (Zhao et al. 2021) or the parasitization (de Barro, Hart and Morton 2000, Zhang et al. 2005) of this parasitoid. *E. formosa* fitness also heavily depends on the host whitefly species. For example, the development of *E. formosa* is faster when the host is *B. tabaci* compared to *T. vaporariorum* (Hu, Gelman and Blackburn 2003). When reared on

Table 3
Summary statistics for *Encarsia formosa* parasitization observations under present (2006–2015) and future climate conditions (2061–2070). n: total number of cages; IQR: inter-quartile range; Q1: first quartile (25th percentile); Q3: third quartile (75th percentile).

Climate	n	Mean	Median	IQR	Q1	Q3
Alive <i>E. formosa</i> adults at 72 h oviposition						
present	10	1.8	2	1	1	2
future	9	1.4	1	1	1	2
Number of 2nd-3rd instar <i>Bemisia tabaci</i> available nymphs						
present	10	73.1	82.5	34.5	54.3	88.8
future	9	168.4	170	76	135	211
Number of visually found parasitized 4th instar exuviae						
present	10	2.0	1.5	3.5	0	3.5
future	9	5.6	5	5	2	7
Total number of emerged parasitoids						
present	10	1.2	1	1.8	0	1.8
future	9	18.2	16	14	13	27

Fig. 3. Joint development curves (left of the dashed line) and longevity curves (right of the dashed line) of F1 adult *Encarsia formosa* under present (2006–2015, green) and future (2061–2070, red) climate conditions. Area under the curve is 28.6, and 27.3 for the present and future curve, respectively. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Table 4

Estimated regression parameters, standard errors, z-values, and p-values for the negative binomial GLMM of *Encarsia formosa* parasitization rate under present (2006–2015) and future climate conditions (2061–2070). Covariates were Climate, Number of available host nymphs, and Number of alive female adults at the end of the 72 h oviposition.

Effects	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)
(Intercept)	2.617585	0.855494	3.06	2.22E-03
Climate present	-2.878475	0.550726	-5.227	1.73E-07
Number of available nymphs	0.035573	0.049354	0.721	0.47105
Alive adults at 72 h oviposition	-0.002428	0.003703	-0.656	0.51194

different species within the *B. tabaci* complex, *E. formosa* exhibits differences in emergence and parasitization rate (He et al. 2017), and may also lead to differences in development time, fecundity, and longevity (He et al. 2019). Moreover, fecundity on *B. tabaci* host is improved if the adults had been conditioned on *T. vaporariorum* (Henter and van Lenteren, 1996). This variability implies that extrapolation of results obtained for one plant-whitefly-parasitoid strain combination must be very limited and that a comparison across studies with different organisms involved is difficult. Therefore, to assess the parasitoid population that is widely used in protected cropping systems, we assessed the development parameters and parasitization of a commercial biocontrol product, Koppert En-Strip, containing ready-to-use *E. formosa* parasitized whitefly nymphs.

It is difficult to compare the results of the present study with previous studies focused on *E. formosa* due to fundamental differences in methodology, and the abovementioned substantial variability in *E. formosa* life parameters. Previous work on this parasitoid was largely focused on obtaining life table parameters where many levels of individual changes in temperature and/or humidity are tested (de Barro, Hart and Morton 2000, Drobňaković et al. 2016, He et al. 2019), and CO₂ concentration typically uncontrolled, with some exception focusing just on CO₂ concentration (Wang et al. 2014). While these studies do accurately examine the response to the changes in the most important environmental variable for the insect development (temperature), they do not consider the daily temperature cycle, nor the interaction of temperature with humidity and CO₂ in physically consistent manner. This makes it

difficult to rely on the life tables for the climate change impact assessment. The present study sets a foundation for and provides initial measured data (as opposed to modelled) for the assessment of parasitoid performance when the research question is the impact of climate change.

It is likely that more frequent parasitoid releases will be necessary as shorter *E. formosa* longevity is anticipated, although applied method cannot conclusively say if the increase in *E. formosa* fitness will counteract the faster whitefly development. Other parameters have to be considered to assess *E. formosa* biocontrol success rate in future climate conditions, such as the parasitoid winter diapause, its metabolic rates and energy reserves, and its dispersal ability. Further, while both *B. tabaci* and *E. formosa* cannot overwinter in the field of Central Europe (Ramos et al. 2018), *B. tabaci* has a reservoir in the protected cropping systems, from which it expands as soon as the conditions allow (Bradshaw et al. 2019). After expansion to the open field, *B. tabaci* in Europe may be parasitized by the already existing populations of oligophagous parasitoids, such as *E. formosa*, which among others also parasitizes *T. vaporariorum* which is spread further to the north than *B. tabaci* (Gerling, Alomar and Arnó 2001). However, other *B. tabaci* specific parasitoids (e.g. *E. eremicus*) must “wait” not only for the abiotic conditions, but also for the sufficient densities of its host to build up the population in the open field (Gerling, Alomar and Arnó 2001). This means that *E. formosa* will likely be an important “first responder” parasitoid in the warmer future climate when seasonal *B. tabaci* infestations in the open field are predicted to gain in significance (Milenovic et al. 2023a). The situation will however be further complicated by the *E. formosa* host range and host preference (Boisclair, Brueren and Van Lenteren 1990, Polaszek, Evans and Bennett 2009).

Finally, the field parasitization rate is likely higher than reported in the present study. The parasitization in this study was evaluated based on the number of adults recovered after the nymphal development of the parasitoid, which excludes any parasitization event that still resulted in the host death, but parasitoid failed to fully develop, or escaped the capture. Further, method of estimating parasitization by counting parasitized exuviae was inferior in the present study and underestimated the parasitization, likely due to the difficulties in discriminating parasitized nymphs obscured by honeydew, waxy secretions, fungal growth and senescing leaves. Our results lay the basis for filling a knowledge gap that will help in the assessment of the effect of climate change on whitefly control methods. To fully describe the efficacy of *E. formosa* in

the future, however, further studies are needed to take into account the lifetime fecundity of a female, longevity in presence of the host, and potentially also flight and host discovery patterns.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Milan Milenovic: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Matteo Ripamonti:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Michael Eickermann:** Methodology, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Carmelo Rapisarda:** Methodology, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Writing – review & editing. **Jürgen Junk:** Project administration, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Writing – review & editing.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocontrol.2023.105354>.

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